

The Role of Data in Advertising and Digital Transformation in Public Relations

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-04, 2024, p. 19– 39. - 0099-0001-2404-0404.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

CURRENT SCIENCE

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with*

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")*

""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""*

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Ali Hami ATILGAN
Northwest University Public Relations and Advertising, PhD
Orcid ID:0009-0005-5443-0625
Email: ahatilgan@gmail.com

[Abstract](#)

Data plays a pivotal role in determining advertising and public relations strategies in the dynamic and always evolving digital environment. The widespread use of digital platforms and technology has given public relations professionals and marketers access to a vast amount of data, which can be utilized to get insights into consumer behavior, preferences, and trends. Data analytics may enhance the capacity of public relations and

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

advertising teams to effectively target their messages, optimize their campaigns, and assess the efficacy of their endeavors. Furthermore, the use of data-driven insights enables public relations and advertising professionals to personalize their messaging and content, leading to more significant and engaging experiences for the intended audience. Data plays a crucial part in developing and executing successful advertising and public relations campaigns, including useful insights derived from social media metrics and website analytics. In order to achieve success in campaigns and maintain a competitive edge, it is essential to

embrace data-driven strategies as the ongoing digital revolution continues to disrupt the public relations and advertising sector. Utilizing and examining data proficiently can not only enhance the efficacy of advertising and public relations endeavors, but also foster a more profound comprehension of client behavior and market dynamics.

Keywords: *Data and Advertising, Advertising, The Role of Data in Advertising, Digital Transformation, Digital Transformation in Public Relations*

Introduction

Data plays a pivotal role in public relations, advertising, and digital transformation, extending beyond fundamental research to include campaign optimization and effect monitoring. Data analytics enables public relations and advertising practitioners to uncover intricate insights into client behavior and preferences, so aiding in the creation of targeted and personalized campaigns.

Through the examination of intricate data, such as individual user interactions and patterns of engagement, public relations and advertising teams may tailor their messaging in order to establish meaningful connections with certain target demographics. An extensive comprehension of consumer behavior acquired via data analysis enables the development of targeted tactics that efficiently cater to the distinct requirements and preferences of diverse demographic segments.

Aim

Utilizing sophisticated data analytics and machine learning technologies enables public relations and advertising experts to forecast forthcoming trends and consumer preferences with enhanced accuracy. Through the use of data-driven analysis, firms may implement a proactive

CURRENT SCIENCE

approach that enables them to predict market trends and adapt their strategies accordingly to meet evolving client demands.

Data plays a crucial part in the digital transformation process by facilitating the creation of enhanced communication channels and engagement platforms. By using data insights, professionals in public relations and advertising may identify emerging digital trends and use the most up-to-date technologies to create compelling brand experiences that effectively engage customers in a constantly evolving digital environment. (Prins, C. and Moerel, L. 2016)

Embracing the Age of Data-Driven Public Relations and Advertising

The integration of data-driven methodologies has revolutionized the realm of public relations and advertising in the rapidly evolving digital era we now inhabit. Technology has significantly changed how consumers behave and communicate, leading to the increasing importance of data in driving public relations and advertising initiatives. Data-driven decision making has brought about a new age of precision and customization in the fields of public relations and advertising. By doing thorough examination of consumer data, organizations may develop focused campaigns and tailor messaging to establish successful connections with certain audience segments. Data-driven insights have not only enhanced advertising effectiveness but also enabled a more profound comprehension of client behavior and preferences (Lahav, T.2014). Our paper aims to analyze this topic from an academic perspective.

Methodology

Public relations and advertising professionals may now use data analytics and machine learning technologies to accurately forecast future trends. By using a proactive approach, bolstered by data-driven research, firms have the capacity to swiftly adjust to evolving client needs and market situations. Data plays a crucial role in the development of innovative communication channels and interactive platforms in the realm of digital transformation. By using data insights,

4

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

professionals in public relations and advertising may identify emerging digital trends and use innovative technologies to develop compelling brand experiences that effectively captivate people in the dynamic digital environment of today (Hawkins, O. 2021).

Literature Review

The integration of sophisticated data analytics and digital innovation is revolutionizing the strategies used by firms to maintain competitiveness and achieve effective campaigns in the era of data-driven public relations and advertising.

Using data to develop focused strategies

As businesses engage in negotiations inside the digital realm, the significance of data in formulating advertising and public relations strategies has notably increased. Data analytics may provide valuable insights into customer behavior and preferences for public relations and advertising teams, enabling them to create targeted and personalized campaigns (Pickavet, Hasselbalch, & Tranberg, 2016).

Utilizing data for decision-making not only enhances the efficacy of campaigns but also enhances comprehension of client behavior and market dynamics. By obtaining comprehensive data, including unique user interactions and engagement patterns, public relations and advertising experts may tailor their messaging to target specific audience segments, leading to enhanced communication and engagement.

Furthermore, the use of sophisticated data analytics and machine learning technologies enables public relations and advertising experts to forecast forthcoming trends and consumer preferences with enhanced accuracy. Through the use of data-driven analysis, firms may implement a proactive approach that enables them to anticipate market trends and adapt their

CURRENT SCIENCE

strategies accordingly to meet evolving client demands. The citation for this work is as follows:
Tauro, D., Panniello, U., and Pellegrino, R. (2021).

Adopting Innovative Communication Channels

Data is essential in the realm of digital transformation and serves as the foundation for developing novel communication channels and interaction platforms. By using data insights, professionals in public relations and advertising may identify emerging digital trends and adopt the most recent technologies to create compelling brand experiences that effectively engage customers in a constantly evolving digital environment.

Organizations are embracing data-driven methodologies in public relations and advertising, including sophisticated data analytics and digital innovation to transform their plans and tactics in order to remain competitive and achieve effective campaigns. The use of data-driven methodologies has revolutionized the domains of public relations and advertising, enabling a more comprehensive comprehension of client behavior and preferences. As a result, this resulted in more robust and triumphant campaigns.

Improving Understanding of Consumer Behavior

The integration of data-driven approaches has provided public relations and advertising professionals with unparalleled access to client behavior and preferences. Organizations may enhance their comprehension of client behavior by scrutinizing intricate data, including individual user interactions and patterns of engagement. The comprehension of this concept has facilitated the development of meticulously tailored strategies that precisely address the requirements and inclinations of many demographic segments, leading to more impactful and significant advertising (Bachstein, S. 2022).

CURRENT SCIENCE

Proficiently using and comprehending data extends beyond a surface-level analysis. This technology has enabled public relations and advertising teams to investigate intricate and intricate insights, resulting in the creation of targeted and customized campaigns that establish strong connections with certain parts of the target audience. The emphasis on precision and customization has elevated the level of communication and interaction, fostering more profound connections between companies and their intended clientele.

Data analytics and machine learning technologies have empowered public relations and advertising professionals to forecast future trends and consumer preferences with exceptional accuracy. Organizations may now use sophisticated data analytics to implement a proactive approach in identifying imminent market shifts and adapting their strategies to align with evolving consumer expectations. This is accomplished by using data-driven intelligence, as described by Komodromos and Nicoli in 2014.

By possessing this proactive and predictive capability, organizations maintain a competitive edge in the market, enabling them to innovate and adjust to evolving client demands quickly and effectively. The use of data-driven intelligence enhances the ability to forecast future trends and promotes continuous innovation and flexibility in a dynamic market.

In summary, the use of data-driven methodologies in public relations and advertising has not only enhanced the efficacy of campaigns but also enhanced our comprehension of client behavior and preferences. The incorporation of sophisticated data analytics and digital innovation has fundamentally revolutionized the strategies and techniques used by organizations, leading to enhanced efficacy and efficiency in marketing and communications endeavors.

[Addressing Ethics and Privacy Issues in Data-Driven Public Relations and Advertising](#)

Data-driven tactics have had a profound impact on the public relations and advertising sector, enabling the creation of targeted and personalized campaigns. Nevertheless, it is essential to

7

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

recognize the ethical and privacy concerns that emerge as a result of the extensive use of customer data.

The thorough examination of consumer data, although beneficial for targeted advertising, raises questions over the privacy and permission of the persons whose data is used. The practice of data mining and using personal data for advertising has generated discussions on ethical concerns and possible infringements on privacy. Furthermore, there is an increasing worry that consumer behavior might be influenced by targeted communication. Adapting marketing efforts to focus on certain audience segments using their distinct data profiles has the capability to leverage psychological susceptibilities and influence client decisions without their conscious awareness. This gives rise to ethical considerations about the boundaries of persuasive advertising tactics. Public relations and advertising professionals need to adeptly use data to develop targeted strategies while safeguarding clients' privacy and autonomy. Given the growing dependence of organizations on data-driven public relations and advertising, it is crucial to prioritize openness and uphold ethical standards. This guarantees that customer data is used in an ethical manner and in compliance with ethical standards and privacy laws.

Amidst the prevalence of data-driven analysis, it is crucial to thoroughly examine ethical considerations around the use of consumer data. This is necessary to maintain public confidence and adhere to ethical standards in the fields of public relations and advertising (Kenan, J. 2023).

Understanding the complex field of ethical considerations

It is crucial for companies to examine the ethical consequences of using consumer data as they navigate the intricate landscape of data-driven public relations and advertising. The thorough examination and use of personal user data for targeted advertising poses significant ethical concerns that need rigorous scrutiny and deliberation.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Confidentiality and permission are crucial ethical considerations. Data mining and the use of personal data for advertising have sparked significant discussions on the ethical ramifications and potential encroachment upon individuals' privacy. Public relations and advertising professionals must acknowledge and tackle these concerns by ensuring that client data is gathered and used with explicit consent and strict respect to privacy regulations.

Moreover, the growing precision of advertising endeavors gives rise to ethical apprehensions over potential manipulation of client behavior. Utilizing distinct data profiles to tailor communications for certain audience segments has the capacity to manipulate psychological susceptibilities and impact decisions without the consumer's complete awareness. Advertising professionals have a moral issue in upholding ethical norms and navigating the boundaries of persuasive tactics in their pursuit of campaign success (Hutchinson, J.2019).

Maintaining transparency and adhering to ethical standards

In the era of data-driven analysis, it is essential to prioritize transparency and ethical principles to ensure the proper use of consumer data in alignment with set standards. Organizations may cultivate trust and showcase their dedication to ethical standards in public relations and advertising by maintaining transparency in data collection and use.

Furthermore, as data analytics and machine learning technologies continue to progress, it is imperative for public relations and advertising professionals to uphold ethical standards when developing and executing targeted advertising campaigns. This encompasses the task of guaranteeing the prudent use of consumer data, safeguarding it from improper use, and exerting utmost effort to safeguard consumers' privacy and autonomy.

Organizations may show their dedication to ethical conduct, maintain consumer trust, and preserve industry standards by proactively addressing ethical issues and prioritizing transparency in their data-driven public relations and advertising endeavors.

CURRENT SCIENCE

As the industry adopts data-driven insights, it is crucial to address ethical considerations about the usage of customer data. It is essential to preserve public confidence and enforce ethical principles in public relations and advertising endeavors. Organizations may exhibit their dedication to responsible and ethical conduct by acknowledging and dealing with these moral repercussions. This enables them to efficiently use data-driven strategies for targeted and efficient marketing.

Analysis of the Results of Data Use

In order to have a more thorough comprehension of the ethical issues related to data-driven public relations and advertising, it is essential to further explore the wider ramifications of data use. The strategic use of consumer data allows for targeted and personalized advertising but requires a thorough comprehension of the possible effects on individuals and society as a whole.

It is crucial to take into account the potential for prejudice and bias while using data. The utilization of data to influence the categorization and focusing of advertisements has the capacity to strengthen or sustain social prejudices. Relying only on historical data for targeting might result in the exclusion or inadequate representation of certain demographics, hence perpetuating inequality and limiting the variety of advertising reach (Hutchinson, E. 2022).¹

Argument

Furthermore, ethical considerations include safeguarding and maintaining the integrity of consumer data. In light of the widespread occurrence of data breaches and the improper use of

¹ The authors of the publication are Chen, H. and Sahm , B. The publication was published in 2019.

CURRENT SCIENCE

personal information, it is imperative for companies to give utmost importance to safeguarding customer data. This is crucial in order to thwart unauthorized access and shield consumers from possible harm or exploitation.

Pursuing comprehensive and morally sound approaches

Businesses must emphasize the implementation of inclusive and ethical procedures when evaluating the ethical issues of data-driven public relations and advertising. This entails taking proactive actions to reduce bias in data analysis and campaign targeting, as well as prioritizing data security procedures to safeguard consumer privacy.

Prioritizing transparency and accountability are crucial to guarantee that consumers are fully informed about the collection and use of their data for advertising reasons. Providing clear and honest information about how data is used builds trust and empowers users to make informed decisions about their interactions with advertising materials. Embracing diversity and inclusion in data-driven campaigns can be a proactive approach to minimize potential bias, ensuring that advertising efforts reach a wide range of audiences and are more successful in marketing communications. can guarantee that it actively contributes to equitable representation.

Re-evaluating Strategies Regarding Data Use

Given the ethical concerns surrounding the use of data for public relations and advertising, organizations must reconsider their approach to data usage. To address this issue, it is necessary to reassess the sources and quality of the data in order to minimize prejudice and formulate a more inclusive approach for targeting campaign efforts.

Incorporating ethical frameworks into the process of developing and executing data-driven strategies may assist companies in successfully addressing ethical problems and minimizing the probability of adverse consequences. Organizations may showcase their dedication to social

CURRENT SCIENCE

responsibility and ethical conduct in their advertising endeavors by giving priority to ethical data practices (Juvana, E. and Lestariningsih, E., 2022).

Ethical concerns surrounding data-driven public relations and advertising extend beyond mere considerations of privacy and openness. In addition, they include the wider ramifications of data use, inclusive methodologies, and influence on society. Organizations may successfully address the difficulties of data-driven advertising and uphold ethical standards and consumer confidence by implementing a complete approach to ethical data use.

Adopting Ethical Data Governance

In order to comprehensively examine the ethical dimensions of data-driven public relations and advertising, it is essential to adopt a meticulous approach to ethical data management. This entails developing explicit standards and procedures for gathering, retaining, and using consumer data, while assuring the adherence to ethical values throughout the entire process.

Ethical data management extends beyond mere legal requirements, placing emphasis on safeguarding consumer privacy and data security, while also ensuring adherence to existing privacy norms. Organizations must use robust data security protocols, such as encryption and access controls, to safeguard consumer data from unauthorized access and potential abuse.

Furthermore, it is crucial for firms to maintain openness in data governance. This entails openly revealing their data practices and furnishing clients with explicit and easily comprehensible details about the gathering, utilization, and safeguarding of their data. This high degree of transparency enhances trust and empowers consumers to make well-informed decisions about their engagement with advertising materials.

Develop a strong understanding of ethical data literacy

CURRENT SCIENCE

Professionals in data-driven public relations and advertising must have a profound comprehension of ethical data practices. Professionals in positions such as data analysts and marketing strategists must possess a thorough comprehension of the ethical ramifications linked to data use. This information is essential for making well-informed and ethically responsible judgments at every phase of a campaign.

Ethical data literacy involves comprehending the technical aspects of data collecting and analysis, as well as recognizing the ethical consequences linked to the use of consumer data. This entails recognizing the potential influence of data-driven campaigns on individuals and society, while also understanding the repercussions of customized messaging on consumer behavior and attitudes. Organizations may cultivate a culture of ethical decision-making and responsible data use in the public relations and advertising workforce by advocating for ethical data literacy. This will demonstrate their dedication to upholding ethical principles in the realm of commerce.

Using Data for Positive Social Impact

Aside from ethical data management and literacy, ethical concerns in data-driven public relations and advertising include the potential use of data for societal benefit. The strategic use of consumer data not only enhances marketing effectiveness, but also enables organizations to leverage data insights to promote social causes and generate positive societal outcomes. This approach necessitates a thorough analysis of the moral consequences associated with using data to connect advertising efforts with initiatives that enhance communal welfare and augment social well-being. Organizations may exhibit their dedication to ethical conduct and use their data assets for the sake of society by incorporating ethical considerations into their choice of campaign actions and issues. In order to adequately tackle ethical issues related to data-driven public relations and advertising, it is necessary to implement a whole approach that encompasses ethical data management, the promotion of ethical data literacy, and the use of data for the improvement of society. By embracing these principles, firms may cultivate a

CURRENT SCIENCE

culture of ethical accountability, foster favorable social consequences, and maintain the integrity of their public relations and advertising endeavors.

Adopting Ethical Data Analytics

In the realm of data-driven public relations and advertising, organizations must give utmost importance to ethical data analytics in order to guarantee that insights and decisions are guided by ethical considerations. This encompasses both the knowledgeable use of consumer data and the ethical examination and implementation of data-driven findings. Ethical data analytics is scrutinizing the methodologies used in data analysis to identify and mitigate any biases that might potentially impact the interpretation of results. Organizations may uphold ethical standards in acquiring insight into advertising campaigns by enhancing transparency in the analytics process and recognizing constraints or patterns in data. In addition, ethical data analytics necessitates thoughtful examination of the possible impacts of advertising campaigns on different demographic segments. Organizations should actively seek to comprehend the influence of their marketing operations on various demographics and guarantee that their analytics techniques exhibit a dedication to advancing fairness and equal representation in advertising. Companies may enhance their dedication to ethical conduct and wise decision-making by using ethical data analytics in public relations and advertising. This, in turn, can bolster trust and credibility in data-driven advertising endeavors.

Analysis of Social Consequences of Data Use

In order to thoroughly examine the ethical dimensions of data-driven public relations and advertising, it is essential to possess a complete understanding of the societal ramifications of data use. One must acknowledge the possible influence of targeted advertising and political campaign language on individuals and communities. Organizations may enhance their decision-making about data-driven projects by taking into account wider societal ramifications. In order to comprehend the societal implications of data utilization, it is essential to

14

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

acknowledge the potential for advertising materials to either strengthen or question existing social norms and biases. A thorough assessment of the contents and imagery used in campaigns is necessary to verify their adherence to ethical standards and their contribution to marketing communications that are more inclusive and equitable.

Moreover, by acknowledging the influence of data-driven public relations and advertising on public opinions and actions, corporations should proactively strive to harmonize their strategies with values that promote diversity, fairness, and social accountability. An extensive comprehension of the societal ramifications of data utilization is essential for the ethical advancement and execution of data-driven advertising initiatives.

Advocating for Inclusive and Diverse Data Sources

In order to uphold ethical standards in data-driven public relations and advertising, it is crucial to advocate for the use of inclusive and varied data sources. Aside from evaluating the data's quality, it is vital to prioritize the ethical collection of data to include the viewpoints and experiences of diverse demographic groups. Promoting inclusivity and diversity in data sources necessitates deliberately seeking out data that precisely represents a broad spectrum of cultural origins, identities, and socioeconomic situations. By using this measure, organizations may decrease the probability of perpetuating prejudices and exclusions in their advertising endeavors and foster a more comprehensive and genuine representation of the intended audience. In addition, organizations may foster a just and inclusive marketing environment by endorsing a wide range of varied data sources. This will aid in guaranteeing that the campaign's targeting and message successfully resonates with a diverse array of clients. This approach is in line with the wider social need for equitable representation in corporate communications and enhances the moral basis of data-driven public relations and advertising. Integrating inclusive and varied data sources not only improves the ethical integrity of data-driven efforts but also shows a dedication to embracing the depth and variety of client experiences in advertising materials.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Public relations and advertising must prioritize the ethical gathering and use of data to provide a more inclusive and equitable approach in marketing communications. Organizations may successfully tackle the ethical dilemmas associated with data-driven advertising by promoting the use of varied data sources and taking into account the social ramifications of data utilization. This thorough and rigorous methodology facilitates the promotion of ethical responsibility and social equality within the sector.

Implementing Ethical Data Governance

Adhering to ethical principles in data management is essential for assuring the meticulous acquisition, retention, and use of client data in the fields of public relations and advertising. The process includes defining explicit rules and procedures for data processing, which encompass gaining permission, safeguarding privacy, guaranteeing data security, and so on. Organizations may enhance consumer trust by prioritizing ethical data management, which entails a firm commitment to safeguarding personal information and upholding privacy rights.

Results

In addition, ethical data governance involves transparent and honest communication of data practices to consumers, allowing them to make well-informed decisions about the sharing of their data and empowering them to have control over their personal information. This proactive approach to data management not only complies with ethical rules, but also enhances client confidence in an organization's data-driven advertising endeavors. In addition, maintaining ethical data governance requires ongoing assessment and modification of data regulations to accommodate evolving legal requirements and industry standards. Organizations must consistently monitor updates in data protection laws and best practices to ensure that their data governance structures remain robust, compliant, and in line with ethical values. Organizations may establish a strong basis for responsible data management, gain consumer confidence, and

CURRENT SCIENCE

distinguish themselves as ethical practitioners in data-driven public relations and advertising by adopting ethical data governance.

Conclusion

Organizations may cultivate an ethical and trustworthy data environment by giving priority to ethical data relationships. This initiative aims to foster cooperation and promote collective accountability in the ethical use of consumer data within the fields of public relations and advertising. Organizations can demonstrate their commitment to ethical responsibility and contribute to the development of a more ethical and fair data use environment in the advertising industry by integrating the principles of transparency, accountability, and ethical data partnerships into their data-driven public relations and advertising initiatives. Furthermore, it is essential for firms involved in data-driven public relations and advertising to use technology in order to uphold ethical data standards. Organizations may uphold ethical standards in data collection, storage, and use by using privacy-enhancing technologies and robust data security measures. Companies may derive valuable insights from data while safeguarding individual privacy and data integrity by using sophisticated methods such as differential privacy, homomorphic encryption, and data anonymization. In order to advance a more ethical and equitable approach to data-driven public relations and advertising, it is crucial to adhere to ethical data governance, support inclusive and diverse data sources, comprehend the societal consequences of data utilization, adopt transparency and accountability, and participate in ethical data collaborations. Furthermore, it is imperative to use technology in order to guarantee ethical data practices, which are essential for upholding ethical standards in the acquisition, retention, and utilization of data. This involves giving priority to establishing an ethical data culture inside the business and actively seeking ethical advancements in data utilization. These steps are crucial for establishing ethical accountability and promoting a more inclusive and fairer environment for data-driven public relations and advertising. These endeavors not only enhance the moral rectitude of organizations' data-driven initiatives, but also cultivate a culture

CURRENT SCIENCE

of ethical advancement and responsibility, resulting in substantial transformation in the sector as a whole.

References

- Bachstein, S. (2022, January 19). The Challenge Facing the Advertising Industry: It's Time to Reduce Bias in Advertising. <https://newsroom.ibm.com/A-Challenge-to-the-Ad-Industry-Its-Time-We-Mitigate-Bias-in-Reklam>
- Bias in advertising: Confronting and overcoming the challenge. (2022, June 28). <https://www.ibm.com/watson-advertising/think-leadership/bias-in-advertising>
- Borg, K., Boulet, M., Smith, L., and Bragge, P. (2018, June 11). Digital Engagement and Health Communication: A Quick Review of the Literature. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10410236.2018.1485077>
- Chen, H. and Sahn , B. (2019, October 4). “Big Data Is Not the Answer to Everything”: Advertising Practitioners' Perception of Big Data. <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/734583>
- Hawkins, O. (2021, August 2). Data in advertising | WPP. <https://www.wpp.com/wpp-iq/2021/07/data-in-advertising>
- Holliman, G. and Rowley, J. (2014, October 7). Business-to-business digital content marketing: marketers' perceptions of best practices. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrim-02-2014-0013>
- Hutchinson, E. (2022, August 17). The Role of Ethics in Emerging Marketing AI. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescommunicationscouncil/2022/08/17/the-role-of-ethics-in-the-evolving-world-of-marketing-ai/>
- Hutchinson, J. (2019, July 18). Digital-first personality: Automation and influence in evolving media ecologies. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856519858921>

CURRENT SCIENCE

IBM Watson Advertising Announces New Research Exploring the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Detecting and Reducing Bias in Advertising. (2021, June 24). <https://newsroom.ibm.com/2021-06-24-IBM-Watson-Reklam-Announces-New-Research-to-Explore-the-Role-of-AI-in-Detecting-and-Mitigating-Bias-advertising>

Juvana , E. and Lestariningsih , E. (2022, January 29). Website Based Sales Information System Design in Isaylees Sports Store. <https://doi.org/10.29040/ijcis.v3i1.58>

Kenan, J. (2023, August 21). AI ethics: How should marketers embrace innovation responsibly? <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/ai-ethics/>

Khan, A. (2014, June 12). Benefits or Advantages of Digital Marketing. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/20140612184227-110373355-benefits-or-advantages-of-digital-marketing>

Komodromos , M. and Nicoli, N. (2014, January 1). The marketing mix: a conceptual framework for teaching public relations and other corporate communications. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijtcs.2014.067834>

Lahav, T. (2014, March 1). Public relations event in new media in Israel 2012: Changing relations. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2013.12.007>

Lemon, A. and Doll-Myers, S. (2018, November 1). Even Old Dogs Can Teach New Tricks: Digital Advertising Assignments Keeping Up with Industry Change. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098048218807145>

Meng, J., Jin, Y. and Hung-Baesecke, F. (2013, December 1). Top issues and responsive strategies in public relations practice: An empirical evaluation in the Greater China region. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2013.07.023>

New Diversity Action Alliance Analysis Reveals Only 21% of PR Professionals Are Racially or Ethnically Diverse. (2021, August 10).

CURRENT SCIENCE

<https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20210810005551/en/New-Diversity-Action-Alliance-Analytics-Finds-Only-21-of-PR-Professionals-Are-Racially-or-Ethnically-Diverse>

Pickavet , H., Hasselbalch, G. , & Tranberg, P. (2016, November 12). Data Ethics -- The New Competitive Advantage. https://techcrunch.com/2016/11/12/data-ethics-the-new-competitive-advantage/?guccounter=1&guc_e_referrer_us=aHR0cHM6Ly90ZWNoY3J1bmNoLWNvbS5jZG4uYW1wcHJvamVjdC5vcmcv&guc_e_referrer_cs=Hp73a ok8 0sewXkn1Ei9rhA

Prins, C. and Moerel , L. (2016, January 1). Privacy for Homo Digitalis: Proposal for a New Regulatory Framework for Data Protection in Light of Big Data and the Internet of Things. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2784123>

Privacy and the Need to Change Marketing: The Battle for Digital Media. (2021, July 22). <https://www.bu.edu/bhr/2021/07/22/privacy-and-the-need-to-change-marketing-a-digital-landscape-war/>

Tauro, D., Panniello , U. and Pellegrino, R. (2021, April 3). Risk Management in Digital Advertising: An Analysis from Advertisers' Media Management Perspective. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14241277.2021.1960532>